

Intramural Ectopic Gestation: Management in a Low Resource Setting

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ABSTRACT

Background: Intramural ectopic gestation, which refers to a pregnancy where the gestational sac is completely within the myometrium is a very rare gynaecological emergency. However, it has the potential for maternal mortality if not diagnosed early and prompt management instituted. Treatment options depend on the severity of clinical presentation, location of the pregnancy within the myometrial wall, viability, and gestational age at diagnosis. This could be expectant management, medical with methotrexate, or surgical which may be via minimal access surgery or laparotomy including hysterectomy. This study presents a case of an intramural ectopic gestation successfully managed medically in a low-resource setting. **Conclusion:** Medical management of intramural ectopic pregnancy is safe and effective in selected cases. It is less invasive and potentially ensures the menstrual and reproductive functions of the uterus.

Keywords: Intramural, Ectopic Gestation, Ectopic Pregnancy, Management

INTRODUCTION

Intramural ectopic gestation or pregnancy is a very rare gynaecological emergency. It constitutes less than 1% of ectopic pregnancies, and only about 70 cases have been reported in the literature as of 2021.^[1,2,3] It refers to a pregnancy where the gestational sac is completely within the myometrium and excludes the endometrial cavity, fallopian tube, and round ligament.^[4,5,6] It could potentially lead to maternal mortality from haemorrhage due to uterine rupture if not diagnosed early and prompt management instituted.^[1,2,5,7] However live birth at 37 weeks of

gestation has been reported in the literature.^[5]

Clinical features of intramural ectopic gestation are non-specific. Patients may present with amenorrhoea, lower abdominal pain, and vaginal bleeding which is similar to other types of ectopic gestation, and miscarriages.^[1] Hypovolaemic shock could be the presentation in patients who have ruptured their uterus.^[8]

Diagnosis is mostly by ultrasonography, Computed Tomography scan, and Magnetic Resonance Imaging in some cases.^[1,2,9] All of these showed evidence of product of conception invasion of the myometrium. Diagnostic Hysteroscopy and Laparoscopy could also be useful.^[8]

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Intramural gestation can easily be misdiagnosed for intrauterine pregnancy or gestational trophoblastic disease.^[8] However intramural gestational trophoblastic neoplasia has also been reported in the literature.^[10]

Risk factors identified in the occurrence of intramural gestation include previous uterine surgery like myomectomy, pelvic adhesions, salpingectomy, dilatation and curettage, assisted reproductive technologies, and adenomyosis.^[5,7,11] These cause decidual and myometrial defects which makes it possible for conceptus to invade and implant within the myometrium. More than 50% of patients with an intramural pregnancy have had a previous dilatation and curettage.^[3]

Treatment options depend on the severity of clinical presentation, location of the pregnancy within the myometrial wall, viability, and gestational age at diagnosis.^[8] Treatment could be expectant management, medical with methotrexate, or surgical which may be via minimal access surgery or laparotomy including hysterectomy.^[1,2,4,8] Uterine artery embolization has also been used for the treatment of intramural ectopic gestation.^[11] Medical management using an injection of potassium chloride into the gestation, also local or systemic methotrexate injection is useful if the diagnosis is made early and there is no rupture, hence fertility is preserved.^[6,10]

A combination of methods can also be deployed as reported by Esther LSY et al where an intramural ectopic pregnancy was managed with suction curettage followed by the use of Bakri balloon tamponade and avoiding hysterectomy. The patient had two doses of methotrexate on account of plateauing serial beta human chorionic gonadotropin levels and undetectable levels was achieved 10 weeks post-methotrexate with complete resolution of intramyometrial ectopic mass.^[6]

CASE REPORT

We present a 33 year old Gravida 4 Para 1⁺² whose only childbirth was 16 years prior to presentation. She had ovulation induction with clomiphene citrate. Following a missed period, she had a positive self-administered urinary pregnancy test.

At 9 weeks gestation by date she experienced a 3-day dull aching, non-radiating lower abdominal pain with

no aggravating or relieving factors. There was also no bleeding per vaginum, abnormal vaginal discharge, or urinary tract symptoms. She went for an ultrasound scan which revealed a bulky uterus with an irregular outline. There was intramural ectopic pregnancy with a fetal pole and no cardiac activity located within the myometrium of the uterine fundus. The gestational sac diameter was 2.34mm, consistent with the gestational age of 7 weeks. Also noted were multiple intramural and subserous myomas with the largest measuring 4.4 by 3.8 cm in the posterior myometrial wall (**Figure 1**).

Her first pregnancy was carried to term and she had a spontaneous vaginal delivery of a live male baby. She had a spontaneous complete miscarriage at 6 weeks and then an incomplete miscarriage at 7 weeks gestational age for which she had manual vacuum aspiration 3 years prior to presentation.

At presentation, she was haemodynamically stable. There was mild abdominal tenderness in the umbilical region and the uterus was 18 weeks size. No significant findings on vaginal examination.

On account of the diagnosis of intramural ectopic gestation, investigations were ordered and the results were as follows. Serum Beta-human Chorionic Gonadotrophin (β -hCG) was greater than 10,000mIU/ml., serum progesterone was within normal limits, serum electrolytes, urea and creatinine as well as liver function tests were within normal limits. Chest x-ray was also normal.

She was admitted into the ward and managed conservatively. She weighed 68kg and had a course of intramuscular Methotrexate 70mg (1mg/kg) on days 1, 3, 5, and 7 with Folinic acid rescue of intramuscular Leucovorin 6.8mg (0.1/kg) on days 2, 4, 6 and 8. She was subsequently discharged and followed up with weekly serum β -hCG assays which showed a steady decline. The Serum β -hCG dropped to 2,212mIU/ml two weeks following treatment, 749.06 mIU/ml in three weeks, 495.88mIU/ml in four weeks. At seven weeks the serum β -hCG was 175.12 mIU/ml and 113.30mIU/ml eleven weeks post treatment. The patient remained asymptomatic throughout the follow up period. She resumed menses 11 weeks after treatment, though with scanty flow over 2 days.

She was not seen again until after 11 weeks due to nationwide industrial action by healthcare workers. That was 22 weeks after treatment. The repeat ultrasound showed bulky uterus measuring 5.24 cm in the maximum antero-posterior diameter with empty cavity and preserved endometrial echoplate. There was no evidence of intramural ectopic pregnancy but there were some fundal intramural fibroids with the largest measuring 5.90 by 4.46cm (**Figure 2**). Repeat serum β -HCG at the time was $<5\text{mIU/ml}$. The patient was reassured of the asymptomatic fibroid and discharged.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

DISCUSSION

Our patient was 33years old and had missed her period for 9 weeks when she presented. This is in line with the mean age of 31.1years with an average gestational age of 10.0 weeks documented in patients with intramural ectopic pregnancy^[1]

She had a history of surgical uterine evacuation of the preceding pregnancy on account of incomplete

miscarriage and also took clomiphene citrate for ovulation induction prior to the pregnancy which is some what in line with assisted reproductive technologies as a less common risk factor.^[11] However, uterine or endometrial surgery is the most documented prominent risk factor.^[1]

The patient presented with ultrasound evidence of unruptured fundal intramural ectopic pregnancy at 7 weeks gestational age hence medical treatment option was adopted. Documented studies showed that fundal location of intramural ectopic pregnancy and gestational age >10 weeks predicts a higher risk of uterine rupture which would have necessitated surgical treatment option^[1] Chaikof M. et al reported a live 8 weeks intramural fundal ectopic gestation. Owing to the unruptured state, presence of a fetal heartbeat and the pregnancy location, a uterine-conserving surgery was performed with fundal hysterotomy and removal of the ectopic pregnancy. The resultant myometrial defect was sutured in multiple layers.^[3] The case we presented was unruptured fundal intramural ectopic gestation but was not alive, hence the non-surgical approach of treatment. Methotrexate is the most commonly used drug and may be administered locally or systemically. Surgery is resorted to if medical management fails. It could be laparoscopically or laparotomy depending on risk of haemorrhage and the surgeons skills^[8]

We administered a four-day course of parenteral methotrexate with folinic acid rescue and the Serum β -hCG dropped from greater than 10,000mIU/ml to less than 5mIU/ml over a period of 22weeks (Approximately 5months). Bannon et al reported a single dose of systemically administered methotrexate and over four months the β -hCG levels progressively dropped but the intramural pregnancy failed to resolve completely, and the persistent mass was eventually removed laparoscopically.^[2] However, in the case we presented the intramural ectopic pregnancy resolved completely after the medical treatment with methotrexate.

Medical management unlike the surgical approach does not afford the opportunity of access to tissue for histology which typically shows large amount of placenta villi within the myometrium.^[8] Histology also helps confirm if the ectopic intramural gestation is

actually not a gestational trophoblastic disease.^[10] Kirk et al described a case of posterior wall intramural pregnancy that was successfully treated by expectant management, as there was no evidence of rupture and the β -hCG levels were quite low (9.5 mIU). During expectant management, the serum β -hCG declined to undetectable levels within 10 days^[4]. Unlike the case we presented, though there was no uterine rupture and there was no cardiac activity, the Serum β -hCG was very high hence expectant management would have been inappropriate.

CONCLUSION

Medical management of intramural ectopic pregnancy is safe and effective in selected cases. It is less invasive and potentially ensures the menstrual and reproductive functions of the uterus.

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